

Questionnaire

on Performance Indicators of E-Business Enterprises in Ukraine

Dear Respondent,

We kindly ask you to participate in this survey aimed at assessing the performance factors of e-business companies in Ukraine.

Your responses will contribute valuable insights for academic research and strategic development within the digital economy.

Please answer all questions accurately and thoroughly. Your cooperation is greatly appreciated

1. Please specify the primary sector of your e-business activity

Select an answer or provide your own answer

	Agricultural Technology (AgriTech)
	Defense Technology (DefenceTech)
	E-commerce
	Educational Technology (EdTech)
	FinTech
	Game Development (GameDev)
	Hardware
	MedTech / HealthTech
	Software as a Service (SaaS)
	Other (please specify)

2. Please indicate the total revenue generated from your business activities in the year 2024

Specify the amount in UAH or EUR

	UAH
	EUR

3. Please indicate the total profit obtained from your business activities in the year 2024

Specify the amount in UAH or EUR

	UAH
	EUR

4. Please specify the total number of staffs by your enterprise (total number)

	Number of persons
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5. Please specify the number of officially employed employees

Notice, question 4 addresses the total number of employees, while question 5 focuses on those with official employment status

	Number of persons
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6. What is the legal form of your business entity?

	Limited liability company (LLC)
	Individual entrepreneur without employees
	Individual entrepreneur with employees
	Other (please specify)

7. What taxation system does your enterprise operate under?

	General taxation system
	Simplified taxation system

8. Please specify the taxes, fees, and mandatory payments paid by your enterprise in 2024

	Income tax
	Single tax
	Personal income tax
	Military duty
	Single social contribution
	Other (please specify)

Thank you very much for your time and valuable input.

Your participation is essential for the success of this research and will help in developing strategies to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of e-business enterprises in Ukraine.